

A METHOD FOR MEASUREMENT OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL CONSTITUTIVE PROPERTIES FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

A. Makeev¹, Y. He², B. Shonkwiler³, E. Lee⁴, H. Schreier⁵, Y. Nikishkov¹

¹ University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX, USA,

² Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA, USA,

³ Clark Atlanta University, Atlanta, GA, USA,

⁴ Bell Helicopter Textron, Hurst, TX, USA,

⁵ Correlated Solutions, Columbia, SC, USA

Keywords: *Polymer-matrix composites; Mechanical properties; Stress/strain curves;*

Abstract

Accurate three-dimensional stress-strain constitutive properties are essential for understanding of complex deformation and failure mechanisms for materials with highly anisotropic mechanical properties. Among such materials, glass-fiber and carbon-fiber reinforced polymer-matrix composites play a critical role in advanced structural designs. A large number of different methods and specimen types currently required to generate three-dimensional allowables for structural design slow down the material characterization. Also, some of the material constitutive properties are never measured due to prohibitive cost of the specimens used for the material characterization. This work shows that simple short-beam shear specimens are well-suited for measurement of 3D constitutive properties for composite materials, and that can enable a major shift toward accurate 3D material characterization. The material characterization is based on the Digital Image Correlation full-field deformation measurement and simple stress analysis. This work introduces three fundamental contributions to the characterization of mechanical properties for composite materials. First, tensile, compressive, and shear stress-strain relations are measured in a single experiment. Second, a counter-intuitive feasibility of closed-form stress and modulus models, normally applicable to long beams, is demonstrated for short-beam coupons. The modulus and stress-strain data are presented for glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy material systems. And third, the test method is viable for measurement of stress-strain relations at various load rates including static, fatigue, and impact load conditions.

Introduction

Analysis of mechanical behavior of materials and structures requires knowledge of material stress-strain constitutive properties. Growing acceptance and rapid development of materials with highly-anisotropic mechanical properties, including glass-reinforced and carbon-reinforced polymer-matrix composites, left accurate characterization of their constitutive properties behind. Structural analysis of composites oftentimes requires accurate assessment of their three-dimensional stress and deformation states to understand complex failure mechanisms [1,2]. Therefore, accurate three-dimensional stress-strain constitutive relations are needed.

Standard techniques for assessment of stress-strain constitutive relations for materials are based on resistance strain gage measurements. As a strain gage measures a “point” strain averaged through the gage area, such measurement imposes constraints on the test specimen designs. For example, a standard practice for assessment of transverse shear constitutive properties for composites is the V-notched beam method [3]. Strain gage measurements in the V-notched beam method drive high specimen cost: at least 0.75-inch (19 mm) thick laminate is required to machine specimens for strain gage placement; and tight geometry tolerances are imposed to minimize variations of strain at the gage location. Also, a large number of different test specimen types used for assessment of constitutive properties, including tensile, compressive, and shear stress-strain curves in the principal material planes [3], slow down 3D material characterization process.

Full-field strain measurement techniques enable additional flexibility for assessment of stress-strain relations, compared to conventional strain gages. High gradient strain distributions can be evaluated. Such flexibility could enable simpler test specimen design and reduce the number of different specimen types required for assessment of 3D stress-strain constitutive behavior. One such technique, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [4] was successfully used in Reference [5] for strain assessment in the nonlinear interlaminar shear stress-strain response of a glass/epoxy tape based on simple short-beam shear (SBS) tests. The SBS test results were in agreement with V-notched beam tests.

It is worth noting that before Reference [5], use of the SBS test method for the development of design allowables for structural design criteria for composites was discouraged in the literature. High-gradient strain distributions in the SBS coupons prohibit the use of strain gages. According to Ref. [6], instrumentation of SBS test coupons was not practical, therefore modulus and stress-strain data could not be obtained. Full-field strain measurements overcame the conventional strain gage limitations in the SBS tests and proved the validity of simple stress models [5] to characterize interlaminar shear stress-strain behavior.

This work generalizes results of Reference [5] and shows that SBS tests and full-field deformation measurement are viable for characterization of tensile and compressive constitutive properties as well as the shear stress-strain curves. In particular, a single SBS test method is required for assessment of the tensile and compressive modulus values, Poisson's ratio, and the shear stress-strain curve in the plane of loading. SBS test coupons are among the simplest to manufacture and test at various load rates. Test specimens could be machined in the zero-degree and 90-degree directions from a single unidirectional panel and loaded in the principal material planes to characterize 3D constitutive relations for composite material systems.

SBS Experiment Description

Glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy unidirectional tape composite SBS specimens machined and loaded in the principal material planes are considered in this

work. Conventional material coordinate notations [6] are utilized. The fiber direction is denoted as 1 (zero-degree); the in-ply transverse direction as 2 (90-degree); and the laminate thickness direction as 3 (interlaminar direction.) The principal material planes are denoted as 1-2 (in-ply), 2-3, and 1-3 (interlaminar planes.)

The American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard [6] guidelines for SBS specimen geometry and boundary conditions for polymer-matrix composites include the specimen width w twice the thickness h , and the support length L four to five times the thickness. In this work, SBS specimen thickness ranges from 0.14" (3.6 mm) for carbon/epoxy to 0.25" (6.4 mm) for glass/epoxy material systems. The width is reduced from the ASTM recommended 200% to about 100% of the specimen thickness for more uniform strain distributions though the width away from the support locations. Also, the loading nose (upper support) diameter is increased from the ASTM standard [5] 0.25" (6.4 mm) to 0.5" (12.7 mm) to reduce compressive damage under the loading nose. Compressive damage issues also result in the reduced SBS specimen thickness required for carbon/epoxy compared to more compliant glass/epoxy composite material systems. A standard [5] lower support diameter is 0.125" (3.2 mm). Figure 1 shows a SBS specimen configuration used in conjunction with DIC full-field strain evaluation.

Fig. 1. Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy SBS Specimen Geometry and Random Surface Texture Created Using Black and White Spray Paints.

Static SBS specimens are placed in a servohydraulic load frame and subject to monotonic load at 0.05 inches/minute (0.021 mm/s) crosshead displacement rate till failure. Figure 2 shows a typical shear failure which started between the loading nose and a lower support and propagated to the specimen edge. The loading conditions are also shown.

Fig. 2. Loading Conditions and Shear Failure of the Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy Tape SBS Specimen

SBS specimens machined in the fiber direction fail in shear, and the specimens machined in the 90-degree direction fail in tension in the middle of the specimen. Figure 3 shows a typical tensile failure for a 90-degree glass/epoxy specimen.

Fig. 3. Tensile Failure of a 90-degree Glass/Epoxy Tape SBS Specimen.

For impact loads, a gravity-based load frame able to generate up to 4 m/s impact velocity was used. The impact weight was 6 lbs (2.7 kg). Figure 4 shows a test setup for impact loading.

Fig. 4. SBS Test Setup for Impact Load Rates.

DIC software VIC-3D [4] is used in this work for assessment of Lagrange strain tensor components on specimen surface. Figure 1 shows a random texture (pattern) created on the specimen surface using black and white spray paints. While the specimen is

subject to load, a sequence of images is acquired using a stereo camera system. The surface strain components are obtained based on analysis of the stereo images. The VIC-3D software determines three-dimensional positions before and after deformation by tracking the gray value pattern in small subsets throughout the acquired stereo image sequence [4].

Figure 5 illustrates typical axial, and shear surface strain distributions in the 1-3 (interlaminar) material plane for 1.75" (42 mm) long and 0.25" (6.4 mm) wide SBS specimens machined from a 26-ply 0.24" thick unidirectional S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy tape panel. Experimental results are labeled as DIC, and results of nonlinear three-dimensional finite element models discussed in the Finite Element Model Substantiation Section are denoted as FEM in the Figure.

Figure 5. Axial (ϵ_{11}), Transverse (ϵ_{33}), and Shear (γ_{13}) Surface Strain Components for a Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy Tape SBS Specimen at 95% Failure Load in the 1-3 Material Plane

Deformation measurements for glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy unidirectional tape composites under quasi-static, fatigue, and impact loading conditions show (a) close to linear axial strain distributions through the SBS specimen thickness far from the support locations, and (b) linear tensile and

compressive stress-strain response till failure. These two observations enable simple closed-form expressions for the tensile and compressive moduli as well as shear stress as shown in the next Section.

Closed-Form Approximations

Linear through the thickness axial strain distributions in the SBS coupons enable simple closed-form solutions for the tensile and compressive moduli as well as shear stresses. A linear axial strain approximation through the thickness is

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = -ky - b, \quad -\frac{h}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{h}{2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6 shows the reference coordinate system.

Fig. 6. Coordinate Notation and Axial Strain Distribution

The thickness coordinate $y = -\frac{b}{k}$ corresponds to the neutral plane location. Neglect the transverse normal stresses away from the support locations and express the linear axial tensile and compressive stress-strain relations (Hooke's Law) as

$$\sigma_{xx} = E_T \varepsilon_{xx}, \quad -\frac{h}{2} \leq y \leq -\frac{b}{k} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{xx} = E_C \varepsilon_{xx}, \quad -\frac{b}{k} < y \leq \frac{h}{2} \quad (3)$$

where E_T and E_C denote the tensile and compressive moduli. The axial force and bending moment approximations for the coupon cross-sections are

$$\iint_{-\frac{h}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{h}{2}} \iint_{-\frac{w}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{w}{2}} \sigma_{xx} dydz = 0 \quad \text{- axial force} \quad (4)$$

$$M = - \iint_{-\frac{h}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{h}{2}} \iint_{-\frac{w}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{w}{2}} \sigma_{xx} y dydz \quad (5)$$

where w is the coupon width. The bending moment is

$$M = \frac{Px}{2} \quad (6)$$

where x is axial distance from the closest lower support and P is applied force.

Substitute Equations (1), (2), and (3) into (4) and (5), neglect the stress variability through the width, integrate and solve (4) and (5) to obtain the following approximations for the tensile and compressive moduli

$$E_{T,C} = \frac{M}{k \frac{wh^3}{12} (1 \mp a)^2}, \quad a = \frac{2b}{hk} \quad (7)$$

As the ratio of the distance $\frac{b}{k}$ between the mid-plane and the neutral plane to the specimen half-thickness is expected to be small such that a^2 is negligible compared to one, Equation (7) also results in the following expression

$$E_{T,C} \approx \frac{M(1 \pm a)^2}{k \frac{wh^3}{12}} \quad (8)$$

The following maximum shear stress approximation in the SBS coupons away from the support locations is derived using expression (8) and force equilibrium in the axial direction on the undeformed beam geometry

$$\tau_{xy} \approx \frac{3P}{4A}, \quad A = wh \quad (9)$$

The maximum shear stress occurs at the neutral plane $y = -\frac{b}{k}$. Expression (9) is a classical approximation for the maximum shear stresses in long beams subject to three-point bending. A nonlinear three-dimensional finite element model was used in Ref. [5] to show that the error of such approximation midway between the loading nose and lower support locations for unidirectional glass/epoxy SBS specimens was within 5%.

As the tensile and compressive modulus values are material properties independent of the x locations, and the bending moment is a linear function of x , the curvature k and the intercept b are also linear functions of x . The linear axial strain approximation (1) for the SBS specimens is generalized as

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = -Kxy - Bx, \quad -\frac{h}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{h}{2} \quad (10)$$

where K and B are constants. Equation (7) can be rewritten as

$$E_{T,C} = \frac{M_c}{k_c \frac{wh^3}{12} (1 \mp a)^2}, \quad a = \frac{2}{h} \frac{b_c}{k_c} \quad (11)$$

where

$$M_c = \frac{Px_c}{2}, \quad k_c = Kx_c = \frac{k}{x} x_c, \quad b_c = Bx_c = \frac{b}{x} x_c \quad (12)$$

and $x_c = \frac{L}{4}$ corresponds to the center cross-section location shown in Figure 6.

The constants k_c and b_c are measured as the slope and the intercept of the normalized axial strain $\frac{\varepsilon_{xx}}{x} x_c$ distributions throughout the SBS specimens away from supports. Please note that the measurements in Equation (11) are not limited to one cross section.

Experimental Results

This Section presents quasi-static constitutive properties for S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy and IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy material systems. First, experimental results are presented for the glass/epoxy composite material system.

To assess 3D quasi-static stress-strain constitutive relations, 15 SBS specimens were machined from a 26-ply 0.24" (6.1 mm) thick unidirectional S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy tape panel. Ten specimens were machined in the fiber (zero-degree) direction and five specimens were machined in the 90-degree direction. The specimens are 1.75" (42 mm) long and 0.25" (6.4 mm) wide. The support length L is 1.2" (30.5 mm).

Fig. 7. Axial Strain Distribution at 95% Failure Load

Fig. 8. Shear Strain Distribution at 96% Failure Load

Five zero-degree specimens were loaded in the 1-3 material plane; five in the 1-2 plane; and five 90-degree specimens were loaded in the 2-3 material

plane. The surface strain components were measured for each specimen in the plane of loading using the DIC technique. Two-mm long gage sections, mid-way between the lower supports and the upper support locations, were used in the assessment of the tensile, compressive, and shear stress-strain material behavior.

Consistent linear through the thickness axial strain distributions were observed for all specimens up to about 95% failure loads. Figure 7 shows a typical normalized axial strain distribution and Figure 8 shows a typical shear strain distribution in the entire gage section. Both distributions show low scatter. Figure 9 shows the interlaminar shear stress-strain response in the 1-3 plane, that is similar to the in-plane shear stress-strain behavior.

Fig. 9. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Shear Stress-Strain Response for Unidirectional S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy Tape

Shear strain in Figure 9 is the average maximum shear strain in the two-mm long gage section. The shear stress approximation is based on Equation 9. For assessment of nonlinear shear stress-strain relations in the 1-3 and 1-2 material planes, Ramberg-Osgood equations [7]

$$\gamma = \frac{\tau}{G} + \left(\frac{\tau}{K} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (13)$$

were used to generalize the experimental results for each specimen using a least squares approximation.

Similar results were obtained in the gage sections in both halves of the specimens.

Table 1 lists the sample averages (AVG) and coefficients of variation (COV) for the parameters in the stress-strain constitutive relations. The trend line shown in Figures 9 is based on AVG constants. For shear strains γ_{13} and γ_{12} exceeding 1%, the SBS specimens exhibit highly nonlinear shear stress-strain behavior. Tensile failure of the 90-degree SBS specimens loaded in the 2-3 material plane occurred at γ_{23} shear strain values between 2,000 and 3,000 $\mu\epsilon$. Linear shear stress-strain response in the 2-3 plane was observed.

Table 1. S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy Constitutive Properties

1-3 Plane	AVG	COV
G_{13} msi (GPa)	0.604 (4.16)	1.56%
K_{13} ksi (MPa)	27.7 (191)	1.47%
n_{13}	0.219	1.93%
E_{11} msi (GPa)	6.82 (47.0)	2.16%
E_{11C} msi (GPa)	6.76 (46.6)	2.07%
ν_{13}	0.27	2.89%
1-2 Plane		
G_{12} msi (GPa)	0.617 (4.25)	3.22%
K_{12} ksi (MPa)	30.7 (21.1)	5.13%
n_{12}	0.237	5.01%
E_{11} msi (GPa)	6.95 (47.9)	0.56%
E_{11C} msi (GPa)	6.79 (46.8)	1.43%
ν_{12}	0.29	3.09%
2-3 Plane		
G_{23} msi (GPa)	0.649 (4.47)	1.20%
E_{22} msi (GPa)	1.82 (12.5)	1.29%
E_{22C} msi (GPa)	1.79 (12.3)	1.39%
ν_{23}	0.41	2.56%

It is worth noting that G_{23} value is close to a transverse isotropic approximation

$$G_{23} \approx \frac{E_{22}}{2(1 + \nu_{23})} = 4.43 \text{ GPa} \quad (14)$$

The Poisson's ratio approximations in Table 1 are based on the axial and transverse strain closest to the tensile (bottom) surface in the center cross-sections between the lower and upper support locations. The Poisson's ratios are calculated as the negative ratios

A METHOD FOR MEASUREMENT OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL CONSTITUTIVE PROPERTIES FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

of the slopes of the applied force – axial and transverse strains. The measured applied force – axial and transverse strain relations were linear till failure. Table 1 lists the average values of the material constitutive parameters measured in the gage sections on both sides of the loading nose.

The measured tensile modulus values for S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy material are similar to the compressive modulus values in the corresponding directions. Higher difference is expected for carbon/epoxy material systems. SBS experiments were accomplished for IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy tape composite in the 1-3 material plane to verify this statement.

Five 20-ply unidirectional IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy tape SBS specimens were manufactured and loaded in the 1-3 material plane to failure. The coupons are 1.05-inches-long (26.7 mm), 0.15-inches-thick (3.8 mm), and 0.12-inches-wide (3.05 mm). Support length is 0.75 inches (19.1 mm). Table 2 lists the nonlinear shear properties as well as the average modulus and compressive modulus values.

Table 2. IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy Constitutive Properties (Material Plane 1-3)

1-3 Plane	AVG	COV
G_{13} msi (GPa)	0.785 (5.41)	1.44%
K_{13} ksi (MPa)	37.4 (258)	7.94%
n_{13}	0.210	7.98%
E_{11} msi (GPa)	23.7 (163)	2.59%
E_{11C} msi (GPa)	21.5 (148)	4.20%

The nonlinear interlaminar shear properties in Table 4 are in excellent agreement with the values $G_{13} = 0.795$ msi , $K_{13} = 37.8$ ksi , $n_{13} = 0.203$ available in open literature for 1.5-inches-long (support length 1 inch), 0.26-inches-thick, and 0.2-inches-wide IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy SBS specimens [8]. The axial modulus data agree with the tensile and compressive modulus values, $E_{11} = 23.8$ msi and $E_{11C} = 21.7$ msi , generated using ASTM standard methods for measurement of the unidirectional tensile and compressive constitutive properties and published by the prepreg manufacturer (Hexcel.)

To show strain rate effect on the interlaminar shear strength and modulus, seven unidirectional S2/E773 SBS were subject to 5.95 lbs impact weight at 4 m/s velocity in the 1-3 material plane. Such impact load resulted in approximately 10^2 strain rate in the SBS coupons. The average interlaminar shear strength value under the impact load increased from 10.4 ksi (static) to 15.2 ksi (46% increase); and the modulus G_{13} increased from 0.604 msi (static) to 0.746 msi (24% increase.)

Finite Element Model Substantiation

To verify accuracy of the closed-form approximations for axial modulus as well as shear stress in the S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy SBS coupons, a nonlinear three-dimensional finite element model (FEM) was built in ABAQUS software [9]. Figure 11 shows a finite element mesh that includes 36,000 C3D20R 20-node quadratic elements with reduced integration. Symmetry boundary conditions were applied to model a half-width of the SBS coupon. Analytical rigid support rollers and frictionless contact conditions were created.

Fig. 10. Finite Element Mesh for a SBS coupon

The FE-models in this work include geometric and material nonlinearities and contact interactions. Geometric nonlinearity accounts for finite displacements. Nonlinear stress-strain response (13) is implemented in the material constitutive model through a user subroutine UMAT in ABAQUS.

FEM predictions for surface strain components the SBS specimens machined and loaded in the 1-2, 1-3, and 2-3 principal material planes are in good agreement with the experimental results (DIC) away from supports. Figure 5 shows the static strain comparison in 1-3 plane for S2/E773 composite.

To study transient dynamics behavior of SBS specimens under impact load, nonlinear explicit finite element analysis has been accomplished in LS-DYNA software [10]. The finite element mesh of impact SBS coupons is similar to its quasi-static counterpart. The steel impactor and drop weight are simplified in the finite element model by a cylindrical rigid body with the same radius as that of the impactor nose, and a prescribed velocity is applied to the rigid impactor to initialize the drop weight impact. A penalty method based surface-to-surface contact algorithm is adopted to simulate the impact interaction. Figure 11 compares the contact force history obtained from a finite element simulation to the measurements for the S2/E773 SBS specimens. The oscillatory contact force due to inertia effects is obtained in the finite element simulation. Figure 12 shows measured and predicted axial strain and interlaminar shear strain contour plots at 95% failure (delamination) load. Good correlation has been achieved. The maximum shear stress far from the support locations is close to the approximation in Equation (9.)

Fig. 11. Contact Force History for Impact Test

Fig. 12. Axial (ϵ_{11}), and Shear (γ_{13}) Surface Strain Components for a Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy Tape SBS Specimen at 95% Failure Load at 10^2 Strain Rate

Conclusions

A method for assessment of three-dimensional material constitutive properties including tensile, compressive, and shear stress-strain relations is developed in this work. The method is based on short-beam specimens subject to three-point bend load, and the digital image correlation full-field surface deformation measurement technique. Tensile and compressive moduli, Poisson's ratios, and shear stress-strain curves in the plane of loading are measured in one short-beam experiment. The concept is demonstrated on S2-Glass/E773-Epoxy tape material system. Short-beam shear specimens machined from a single panel the principal material planes were utilized. Linear axial strain distributions through the specimen thickness were observed. Such observation allows for simple closed-form approximations of the tensile and compressive moduli as well as shear stresses. A small difference between tensile and compressive modulus values for the glass/epoxy composite prompted another demonstration for IM7-Carbon/8552-Epoxy tape composite with a known lower compressive modulus compared to the tensile modulus in the fiber direction. Simplicity of the short-beam specimens and accuracy of the constitutive property approximations make the

presented experimental method attractive for measurement of three-dimensional stress-strain relations for anisotropic materials at various load rates.

And it is worth noting that the strong strain rate sensitivity of interlaminar properties makes the characterization of material constitutive properties at high strain rates essential for models that capture the matrix-dominated failure modes and their interaction under the impact load conditions.

Acknowledgements

This work is sponsored by the US Office of Naval Research and the National Rotorcraft Technology Center, U.S. Army Aviation and Missile Research, Development and Engineering Center (ARMDEC.) Such support is gratefully acknowledged. The views and conclusions contained in this article should not be interpreted as representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the U.S. Government.

References

- [1] Dobyns, A., Rousseau, C. Q., and Minguet, P. (2000). In: *Comprehensive Composite Materials*, Kelly, A. and Zweben, C. (Eds.), Elsevier Ltd., Vol. 6, pp. 223-242.
- [2] U.S. Department of Defense (2002). Military Handbook - MIL-HDBK-17-1F: Composite Materials Handbook, Volume 1 - Polymer Matrix Composites Guidelines for Characterization of Structural Materials.
- [3] American Society for Testing and Materials (2005). Standard Test Method for Shear Properties of Composite Materials by the V-Notched Beam Method, ASTM Standard D 5379/D 5379M, ASTM International.
- [4] Sutton, M. A., Orteu, J.-J., and Schreier H. W. (2009). *Image Correlation for Shape, Motion and Deformation Measurements*, Springer.
- [5] Makeev, A., Ignatius, C., He, Y., Shonkwiler, B. (2009), *J. Comp. Mat.*, 43 (25), pp. 3091-3105.
- [6] American Society for Testing and Materials (2006). Standard Test Method for Short-Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates, ASTM Standard D 2344/D 2344M, ASTM International.
- [7] Jones, R. M. (1999). *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Second Edition, Taylor & Francis, Inc.
- [8] Makeev, A., Seon, G., Lee, E. (2010) Failure Predictions for Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminates with Wavy Plies, *J. Comp. Mat.*, 44 (1), pp. 95-112.
- [9] Simulia (2009), ABAQUS V6.10 User Manual.
- [10] LSTC (2006). LS-DYNA Theory Manual.